

Studies in Azomethine Azo-Dyes.¹

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From a study of the tinctorial properties of a series of azomethine azo-dyes—containing a single azomethine group in the *para*-position to the azo-group but without any auxochromic group in the molecule—prepared by Green and Sen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 97, 2242), it was found that the shade of an azo-dye remains practically unaltered by the introduction of an azomethine group.

The present work has been undertaken for further studies in azomethine azo-dyes in respect of (1) the effect of introducing an additional azomethine group in the *para*-position to the azo-group, and (2) the effect of an auxochrome (OH) in the *para*-position to the azo-group.

A dialdehyde, *viz.*, azo-benzaldehyde-sulphonic acid [$\text{CHO}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{SO}_3\text{H})\cdot\text{N}_2\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{SO}_3\text{H})\cdot\text{CHO}$] obtained from "Mikado orange"

in the manner described by Green and Leonhardt (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 86, 1613) was selected for the preparation of dyes, containing two azomethine groups in the *para*-positions to the azo-group but without any auxochromic group in the molecule. The dialdehydic nature of the compound has been fully investigated and established in this work, and by its condensation with different amino-compounds and several dyes containing free amino-groups, the first type of dyes has been obtained.

The condensation products of the dialdehyde with several monoamines, such as aniline, α -naphthylamine and β -naphthylamine, produce on wool shades (varying from yellow to brown) considerably lighter than the shade (orange) obtained with the dialdehyde. This shows that the introduction of two azomethine groups makes the colour lighter. This appears to be in perfect

¹ The delay in the publication of the paper is due to the sudden death of one of the authors.

agreement with the conclusion arrived at by Sen and Sett (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 111) namely, that too much multiplication of chromophores tends to make the colour lighter. The compounds in the solid state possess colour from yellow to reddish brown and give differently coloured solutions in strong sulphuric acid. The aniline compound gives a yellowish-red solution, the α -naphthylamine compound a reddish-brown solution and the β -naphthylamine compound gives a dark-brown solution, whereas the dialdehyde itself gives an orange-red solution.

The presence of free amino-groups in the condensation product (I) of the dialdehyde with semicarbazide is confirmed by the evolution of nitrogen by the action of nitrous acid. It dyes wool in golden-yellow shade which is lighter than that (orange) produced by the dialdehyde. The compound possesses a yellow colour and gives a yellowish-red solution in concentrated sulphuric acid.

(I)

The absence of any free amino- or any free aldehyde group in the condensation products of the dialdehyde with the diamines namely hydrazine, *o*-phenylene diamine, *p*-phenylene diamine and benzidine, indicates that the aldehyde and the diamine react in molecular proportions with the elimination of two or four molecules of water, giving rise to polymembered ring structures (II or III).

(II)

(III)

Such ring structures are supported by a recent work of Adams, Bullock and Wilson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 521). The general properties, such as extreme insolubility, and high melting points referred to in that work, are very similar to those of the condensation products of benzidine and *p*-phenylene diamine with the azo-aldehyde. The molecular weight could not be determined owing to the great insolubility of the compounds, and for the sake of simplicity the structure (II) has been given.

The colour of the compounds obtained by condensing *p*-phenylene diamine and benzidine with the dialdehyde is almost the same, although one contains a phenyl and the other a diphenyl residue. The behaviour of the two compounds towards concentrated sulphuric acid is however interesting. The benzidine compound dissolves in sulphuric acid with a violet colour, but on dilution with water a red precipitate is thrown down and the solution becomes colourless; whilst the *p*-phenylene diamine compound produces a red colour in concentrated sulphuric acid, which on dilution changes to light-violet. It is very difficult to study the dyeing properties of these compounds owing to their insolubility and ready tendency to hydrolyse. The compound obtained from hydrazine gives a red solution in sulphuric acid and dyes wool in orange shade, while the compound obtained from *o*-phenylene diamine dyes wool in fine canary yellow shade and dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with yellowish-red colour. The deepening of colour in the hydrazine compound is presumably due to the presence of the aldazine group ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{CH}-$).

The dialdehyde has further been condensed with several dyes (containing free amino-groups) such as safranin, rosaniline and chrysoidine and in every case the colour becomes lighter than that of the original dye. The reactions with safranin and rosaniline are found to occur in molecular proportions and the usual ring formation is also supported in these cases by the absence of free amino- and CHO groups. It is interesting to note that in the case of chrysoidine (with two amino-groups in *meta*-position) two molecules of the aldehyde react with three molecules of the chrysoidine (IV).

In this connection a noteworthy observation has been made that the dyes rosaniline and safranin can be estimated quantitatively by titrating with a standard solution of the dialdehyde, using phenylhydrazine acetate solution as an external indicator.

With a view to study the effect produced on azomethine azo-dyes by the presence of an auxochromic group (OH), a monoazo-aldehyde with an OH-group in the *para*-position to the azo-group, *viz.*, salicylazobenzaldehyde-sulphonic acid [CHO·C₆H₃(SO₃H)·N₂·C₆H₃(OH)·COOH] has been prepared from 'Hessian yellow.'

A few compounds were obtained by the condensation of the mono-azoaldehyde with amino-compounds. By way of comparison it may be noted that they produce on wool similar shades as those obtained from the corresponding compounds of phenetoleazobenzaldehyde-sulphonic acid (Green and Sen, *loc. cit.*)

Thus from a study of the compounds described in this paper, it is found that in azomethine azo-dyes—(1) the effect of introducing an additional azomethine group in the *para*-position to the azo-group lightens the colour more or less, except in the case of two azomethine groups in juxtaposition, constituting the aldazine group which deepens the colour; (2) the presence of an auxochromic group (OH) in the *para*-position to the azo-group, like the auxochrome in the *para*-position to the azomethine group (previously studied by Green and Sen) has practically no effect.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(A) Sodium *p*:*p'*-Dialdehyde-azobenzene-*m*:*m'*-disulphonate.

To a filtered solution of "Micado orange" (40 g.) in boiling water (2.5 litres), cooled to 0–5°, a 3% solution of potassium permanganate (2.36 g.) is added gradually until a permanent pink colour is obtained, the solution being mechanically stirred during the addition. After the reaction is complete the solution is boiled, filtered from the manganese dioxide sludge and the residue repeatedly extracted with hot water. After neutralisation by hydrochloric acid, the combined filtrates are concentrated to a small bulk on the water-bath and the sodium salt of the sulphonic acid precipitated by the addition of common salt. The sodium salt is collected, washed with

alcohol (50%) and purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol, when it is obtained in buff-coloured microscopic needles. A further quantity of less pure material can be obtained by the further addition of common salt to the original filtrate (yield, 67.5%). The disodium salt is readily soluble in water and the sulphonic acid is not precipitated by the addition of acid. On treatment with phenylhydrazine it yields a reddish-brown phenylhydrazone. It dissolves in sulphuric acid yielding an orange-red solution which on dilution becomes orange and finally yellow. It dyes wool an orange shade. (Found: N, 6.29, 6.34; S, 14.65, 14.77. $C_{14}H_9O_8N_2S_2Na_2$ requires N, 6.33; S, 14.48 per cent.).

The *barium salt* is insoluble in cold water and slightly soluble in hot water. (Found: Ba, 25.91, 25.94; N, 5.17, 5.20. $C_{14}H_9O_8N_2S_2Ba$ requires Ba, 25.75; N, 5.24 per cent.).

A determination of the aldehyde groups is effected by titrating with a standard solution of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate, employing phenetoleazobenzaldehyde-sulphonic acid as an external indicator. (Found: CHO, 13, 12.8. $C_{14}H_9O_8N_2S_2Na_2$ requires CHO, 13.12 per cent.).

Preparation of the Azomethine Azo-dyes.

(1) *Condensation product with semicarbazide* is prepared in the usual manner and is crystallised from hot water. It is a yellow substance, moderately soluble in cold water, soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellowish-red colour which changes to yellow on dilution; it dyes wool in golden-yellow shade. (Found: N, 20.09, 19.98. $C_{16}H_{14}O_8N_4S_2Na_2$ requires N, 20.14 per cent.).

(2) *Condensation product with aniline*.—A hot solution of aniline (1.4 c.c.) in dilute acetic acid is slowly added to a hot aqueous solution of the aldehyde (3 g.), the mixture being stirred all the time and the reaction completed by warming for a short time. The yellow precipitate, thus obtained, is filtered off, washed with dilute acetic acid and is crystallised from hot water. It is a yellow powder, sparingly soluble in cold water, soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellowish-red colour, which changes to yellow on dilution; dyes wool a yellow shade. (Found: N, 9.57, 9.64. $C_{26}H_{18}O_6N_4S_2Na_2$ requires N, 9.46 per cent.).

Other condensation products with the mono-amines are listed in Table A.

(3) *Condensation product with benzidine.*—To a cold acidified aqueous solution of the aldehyde (4 g.) a solution of benzidine (1%) in hydrochloric acid is slowly added till the solution is almost colourless, when a dark-brown precipitate separates in the cold. The precipitate is filtered off, thoroughly washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, then with hot water and hot alcohol and dried; the free compound, thus obtained, is dark-brown, insoluble in hot water, slightly soluble in caustic alkalis, practically insoluble in hydrochloric acid, which hydrolyses the compound on heating. It is sparingly soluble in alcohol and practically insoluble in other organic solvent, soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid with a violet colour and on dilution a red precipitate is thrown down; it dyes wool a brownish-yellow shade. (Found : N, 10.03, 9.89. $C_{26}H_{18}O_6N_4S_2$ requires N, 10.25 per cent.).

Other condensation products with the diamines are listed in Table A.

(4) *Condensation product with chrysoidine.*—A hot aqueous solution of the aldehyde (4 g.) is added drop by drop to a solution of chrysoidine (3 g.) in dilute hydrochloric acid, heated to 70-80°. The solution is then vigorously stirred until it is cold. The precipitate, thus obtained, is filtered, washed with hot water and hot alcohol; the free compound, thus obtained, is a scarlet powder, insoluble in water and in acid, slightly soluble in caustic alkalis. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a scarlet-red colour changing to reddish-orange on dilution; it dyes wool a yellow shade. (Found: N, 16.26, 16.31; S, 9.32. $C_{84}H_{48}O_{12}N_{16}S_4$ requires N, 16.47; S, 9.40 per cent.).

Condensation products with safranine and rosaniline are listed in Table A.

(B) *Sodium Salicylasobenzaldehydesulphonate.*

It was prepared by the oxidation of a solution of 'Hessian yellow' (Merck) (30 g.) in water (3 litres) with potassium permanganate solution (3%, 6.6 g.) in the manner described in the preparation of the dialdehyde. The isolation and the purification of the compound was similarly carried out (yield, 70%). The free compound, obtained as reddish-orange microscopic needles by crystallising the sodium salt from hot water acidified with hydrochloric acid, is moderately soluble in cold water. It reacts very easily with phenyl-

hydrazine producing an orange phenylhydrazone. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red colour, which on dilution changes to yellow ; sodium hydroxide solution produces a deep red colouration ; it dyes wool an orange (slightly yellowish) shade. (Found: N, 7.96, 8.04 ; S, 9.24. $C_{14}H_{10}O_7N_2S$ requires N, 8.0 ; S, 9.14 per cent.).

A determination of the aldehyde group is effected in the manner described in the case of the dialdehyde. (Found : CHO, 8.19, 8.27. $C_{14}H_{10}O_7N_2S$ requires CHO, 8.29 per cent.).

The azomethine azo-dyestuffs prepared from the mono-aldehyde are listed in Table B.

TABLE A.

Formula.	Preparation.	Found. %	Analysis. Calc. %	Shade on wool.	Properties.
(5) $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S_2$	Aqueous solution of the dialdehyde (3 g.) + alcoholic solution of β -naphthylamine (1.9 g.) on the water-bath.	N, 8.0, 8.01	N, 8.09	Greyish-orange.	Crystallised from dilute alcohol; a bright orange powder, moderately soluble in cold water, soluble in conc. sulphuric acid (dark-brown solution).
(6) $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2S_2$	Aqueous solution of the dialdehyde (2.21 g.) + solution of α -naphthylamine (1.48 g.) in dilute hydrochloric acid on the water-bath.	N, 8.54, 8.62	N, 8.64	Brown.	Crystallised from dilute alcohol; the free compound is reddish-brown, slightly soluble in hot water, readily in alcohol.
(7) $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2S_2$	The dialdehyde (3.31 g.) + <i>o</i> -phenylene diamine (8 g.) + glacial acetic acid on the water-bath.	N, 10.86, 10.82	N, 10.89	Fine canary yellow.	Crystallised from dilute alcohol; yellow powder with a slight orange tinge; sparingly soluble in cold water, soluble in conc. sulphuric acid (yellowish-red, changing to yellow on dilution).
(8) $C_{10}H_{11}O_2N_2S_2$	By mixing molecular proportions of acidified solution of the dialdehyde and <i>o</i> -phenylene diamine in the cold.	N, 11.81, 11.72	N, 11.91	Chocolate.	Reddish-brown free compound, insoluble in water, slightly soluble in caustic alkalis, sparingly in hot alcohol, soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid (red, changing to violet on dilution).

TABLE A (continued).

Formula.	Preparation.	Found. %	Analysis. Calc. %	Shade on wool.	Properties.
(9) $C_{11}H_{10}O_6N_4S_4Na_2$	Aqueous solution of hydrazine sulphate (0.64 g.) and dialdehyde (2.3 g.) on the water-bath.	N, 19.74, 12.68	N, 19.79	Bright orange.	Deep orange sodium salt, fairly soluble in cold water, soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid (red, changing to yellow on dilution).
(10) $C_{13}H_{11}O_6N_4S_4$	The dialdehyde + rosaniline hydrochloride in the same manner as in (4).	N, 10.44, 10.46	N, 10.7	Bluish-red.	The free compound has a deep chocolate colour, moderately soluble in hot water, easily soluble in alcohol, soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid (brownish-red).
(11) $C_{11}H_9O_6N_4S_4$	The dialdehyde + safranine in the same manner as in (4).	N, 12.84, 12.26	N, 12.10	Red.	The free compound is a chocolate-coloured powder, moderately soluble in hot water and in alcohol.

TABLE B.

Formula.	Preparation.	Found. %	Analysis. Calc. %	Shade on wool.	Properties.
(1) $C_{10}H_{11}O_4N_2S$	The aldehyde + aniline acetate.	N, 9.85, 10.05	N, 9.88	Fast yellow.	Yellow powder, readily soluble in alcohol, sparingly soluble in cold water.
(2) $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2S$	The aldehyde + benzidine hydrochloride.	N, 9.88, 9.94	N, 9.91	Yellow.	Reddish-orange powder, slightly soluble in water and moderately in hot alcohol.
(3) $C_{11}H_{10}O_4N_2S$	The aldehyde + chrysoidine hydrochloride.	N, 12.88, 12.89	N, 12.76	Yellow.	Red colour, slightly soluble in water, easily soluble in hot alcohol.
(4) $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2S$	The aldehyde + rosaniline hydrochloride.	N, 10.14, 10.28	N, 10.29	Bluish-red.	Deep chocolate colour, sparingly soluble in cold water, freely soluble in hot alcohol.
(5) $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_2S$	The aldehyde + safranin hydrochloride.	N, 11.82, 11.94	N, 11.23	Red (slightly orange).	Chocolate colour, slightly soluble in hot water, but more soluble in alcohol.

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